

29 Highlights

- 30 • Vaccine profitability and affordability can be enhanced by orchestrating how and when markets buy
31 vaccines, even for a non-cooperative system.
- 32 • Vaccine affordability for low-income and low-middle-income countries can be improved if they pool-
33 procure via multiple coordinated entities, while high- and upper-middle-income countries buy vaccines
34 via fewer but larger pool-procuring groups.
- 35 • Pool-procurement groups for low- and low-middle-income countries should have multiple price levels
36 per vaccine to enhance affordability, which opposes the current single-price strategy followed by multi-
37 lateral organizations for most pediatric vaccines.
- 38 • The order of procurement can enhance affordability for different vaccine market segments.

1 Introduction

Pediatric vaccines are credited for saving more than 2 million lives every year [1]. They are among the most cost-effective public healthcare interventions ever employed, as treating ill patients is more expensive than preventing diseases through immunization [2]. Whitney et al. [3] estimates that in the US alone, pediatric vaccines saved over \$1.38 trillion in total societal costs between 1994 and 2013.

The global pediatric vaccine market consists of countries that procure vaccines from a limited set of producers to satisfy their immunization needs. High- and upper-middle-income countries typically buy vaccines on their own via public and private purchases. In contrast, lower-income countries rely on pool procurement and tiered pricing to take advantage of economies of scale and secure better prices [4, 5]. For example, over thirty Latin American countries procure vaccines as a group through the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO)’s Revolving Fund. Similarly, the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) procures vaccines for nearly 70 low- and lower-middle-income countries eligible to receive financial support from donors such as Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance. Gavi is a multi-lateral organization with private and public donors that works to improve affordable vaccine access in the poorest countries of the world [6]. All countries buying vaccines through either PAHO’s Revolving Fund or UNICEF pay the same price per dose for a given vaccine, although Gavi has different co-financing levels with different countries.

Pooled procurement also benefits vaccine producers. By securing more affordable vaccines for low-income countries, PAHO, UNICEF, and Gavi have established a more stable and predictable pediatric vaccine demand [7], facilitating their manufacturing and allowing producers to use tiered pricing to push vaccine inventories [8]. Furthermore, PAHO and UNICEF act as coordinators between buyers and producers. These coordinators negotiate vaccine prices at the most affordable levels for their countries while ensuring that the vaccine market remains financially attractive without jeopardizing future supply at such prices. Although PAHO and UNICEF collaborate, they purchase independently to secure supplies for their countries. Consequently, PAHO and UNICEF have each their own pricing levels. A situation in which buyers negotiate independently with limited cooperation can increase the number of possible market configurations: whether some buyers are prioritized over others and how pricing decisions differ between buyers. Those complications could be modeled and studied as hypothetical scenarios to determine their effect on buyers and producers.

Through tiered pricing, producers set different price levels for a vaccine depending on the buyers’ income levels [8]. Traditionally, vaccine producers have grouped countries into four tiers (market segments): high-, upper-middle-, low-middle-, and low-income countries, following The World Bank country classification (see Table 1); but some producers have their own tier structures for different vaccines. Reselling low-priced vaccines to higher-income countries is usually not feasible due to market regulations, cold-chain logistics

Classification	Abbreviation	Lower Country GNI Limit (US\$)	Upper Country GNI Limit (US\$)
High-income countries	HIC	12,055	-
Upper-middle-income countries	UMIC	3,896	12,055
Lower-middle-income countries	LMIC	996	3,896
Low-income countries	LIC	-	995

Table 1: World Bank 2021 classification for countries based on income [9].

71 restrictions, and differences in immunization schedules. Pooled procurement and tiered pricing are not
72 mutually exclusive, so even countries cooperating in the vaccine negotiation may not pay the same prices if
73 they are in different market segments.

74 Despite the positive effect of tiered pricing and pooled procurement, pediatric vaccines are not always
75 available and affordable for low-income countries. The World Health Organization (WHO [10]) estimates
76 that 19.5 million infants did not have access to essential vaccines in 2018 [10, 11, 12]. The attention given to
77 other emergencies, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, could also result in the reallocation of funds away from
78 established immunization programs, which compete for the same logistical capacity for delivering and storing
79 vials. Unless immunization programs are fully restored, and access to affordable vaccines strengthened,
80 COVID-19 interruptions to routine immunization programs could result in more than a million deaths
81 among African children [13]. There are additional reasons for the lack of access to pediatric vaccines,
82 including (1) the vaccine supply by volume is highly concentrated in a limited number of producers [2]; (2)
83 the monetary value of the vaccine market is concentrated on sales to high-income countries; (3) logistics
84 factors affect vaccine distribution and increase costs; (4) weak local immunization programs; (5) political
85 turmoil disrupting immunization campaigns; and (6) low national health investments.

86 This study explores how uncertainties derived from pooled procurement and tiered pricing affect countries
87 with different income levels. To that end, we consider a hypothetical globally-coordinated pediatric vaccine
88 market where demand for multiple antigens is met via a single tender¹. In this pediatric global vaccine
89 market, multiple coordinating entities procure doses on behalf of countries grouped into market segments
90 based on their income level.

91 In contrast to UNICEF’s and PAHO’s single-price markets, it is assumed that each coordinating entity
92 can have multiple price levels per vaccine (i.e., it can negotiate on behalf of different market segments).
93 The entities make vaccine procurement decisions that foster an affordable and profitable vaccine market
94 by determining the optimal amount of vaccines to buy at each of their market segments and the range of

¹An antigen is a substance that provokes an immune response to a particular disease. (e.g., polio vaccines offer antigens that induce a response to Polio viruses. Combination vaccines such as DTP offer antigens against Diphtheria, Tetanus, and Pertussis in a single dose)

95 affordable prices that ensure a desired profitability for the producers. We consider a vaccine affordable to
96 a market segment if its price per dose is lower than its average willingness-to-pay among the countries in
97 the market segment. Furthermore, it is assumed that the coordinating entities are trusted intermediaries
98 that seek no financial benefit for themselves and do not cooperate with each other in making their procuring
99 recommendations.

100 We consider that during a procuring cycle (e.g., a year), non-cooperative entities buy vaccines to clear
101 their markets' antigen demands through a sequence of negotiations with the producers. This procuring
102 sequence is important since a successful negotiation reduces the available supply for other entities in sub-
103 sequent negotiations. Furthermore, producers can offer discounts to push inventory, affecting subsequent
104 procurement decisions. In this study, the coordinating entities' procuring order is based on the average
105 income of their represented countries. We explore an ascending and a descending procuring order.

106 In this study, the investment costs to manufacture vaccines are annualized. These costs incorporate
107 a desired return on investment high enough to cover fixed costs for the commercialized vaccine products'
108 research, development, and manufacturing. Under a market with non-cooperative coordinating entities, it is
109 assumed that producers can follow two policies to recover their annualized fixed costs: (1) offering discounts
110 on vaccines whose supply has been partially sold to other entities, and (2) offering no discounts.

111 Under this framework, we investigate the effects of four relevant factors on the global affordability and
112 profit: (1) the number of market segments in which countries are grouped, (2) the number of coordinating
113 entities in the global vaccine market, (3) the order those coordinating entities follow to buy vaccines, and
114 (4) whether producers push their products via discounts.

115 To address the effect of those factors, we extend the mathematical framework proposed by Proano et al.
116 [14], which determines vaccine procurement plans for a globally coordinated vaccine market with a single
117 coordinating entity. We enrich this framework to handle a fragmented global vaccine market where multiple
118 entities can make non-cooperative procurement decisions sequentially. Due to this sequential negotiation,
119 the producers have the option of discounting their vaccine prices at subsequent negotiation rounds. The
120 framework proposed in this study permits exploring the isolated effect of a varying level of procurement
121 cooperation among numerous coordinating entities.

122 This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature on pediatric vaccine pricing and
123 group buying studies. Section 3 describes the mathematical model and the three-stage optimization process,
124 the experimental framework, and the performance metrics used in this study. Sections 4 and 5 describe the
125 experimental data and the study's results. Finally, Section 6 offers a discussion and relevant extensions.

2 Literature Review

This section reviews the literature on group buying and mathematical modeling of pediatric vaccine pricing. Although there is abundant literature on general group buying and its effects on tiered pricing [15, 16, 17, 18], we are unaware of studies considering group buying for vaccines. Vaccine pricing studies that rely on mathematical programming models have focused on the pricing of a new vaccine into a single competitive market or its logistic distribution within that market [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24]. Proano et al. [14] proposes a mathematical programming model and a three-stage optimization-based process to explore a hypothetically coordinated vaccine market where the number of vaccines to buy and their prices maximize affordability and profit. From an economic perspective, several studies question the mechanisms through which pediatric vaccines are sold and how they affect their affordability [25, 26, 27, 28]. Studies on vaccine pricing based on cost-benefit analysis vary broadly and without consensus, highlighting the difficulty of valuing preventive care and saving lives over multiple regions [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34].

The literature on group buying focuses on pool procurement and its effect on affordability and profit. It considers scenarios with unlimited supplies, a single product, a producer, and an online mediator that charges membership fees to allow customers access to price discounts [15, 16, 17, 18]. These assumptions are used in modeling frameworks that capture the relationship between order quantities, price, and the benefit of joining a group. Those assumptions may not adequately fit the characteristics of the vaccine market, which has no membership fees to access discounted prices. In the global vaccine market, countries need to meet other criteria to be part of a group, such as being in a geographical region or having specific income levels.

Hu et al. [15] assumes that a set of customers can be coordinated into group buying entities negotiating online deals with a single seller. The study deals specifically with sequencing buyers, as the negotiating order can affect whether or not there is enough demand to justify the deal. Hu et al. [15] relies on game theory to model the interaction between customers and the seller, considering a sequence of discrete interaction periods in which several customers may choose independently. Buyers in the study have the option of not satisfying their demand or choosing outside sources not represented in the model.

Under a general coordinated group-buying framework, Yang et al. [16] studies the conditions that might make it more advantageous for sellers to serve each participating buyer in a given market. The study assumes that the seller can obtain other business if the entities refuse to negotiate.

Chen and Roma [17] models group-buying through a three-step process involving producers, retailers, and buyers. Retailers can choose whether to cooperate with a group-buying entity or not. Assuming a linear demand, Chen and Roma [17] suggest that group-buying might be more advantageous to smaller, less powerful retailers than to bigger ones under a non-cooperative environment.

158 Anand and Aron [18] considers group-buying mechanisms for a monopoly on web-based transactions under
159 uncertain demand. Customer product valuations are uncertain and unknown. However, such uncertainties
160 may not hold for the vaccine market [35]. Any variations in purchased quantities are more likely to come
161 from changes in available budgets, existing stockpile levels, reactions to outbreaks, logistical issues, and
162 political instabilities than from birth rate changes.

163 Game theory models have been the core of several studies on vaccine pricing decision problems [19, 20,
164 21, 22, 23]. These studies have focused on the impact of new vaccines in a single market, ignoring the
165 implications of potential buyer coordination.

166 Robbins et al. [21] uses a game theory model to frame the US vaccine market as an oligopoly of asymmetric
167 producers in a Bertrand competition where each producer can supply the entire market. The paper proposes
168 a mathematical approach to capture oligopolistic interactions for the US market that result in different
169 pricing strategies.

170 Other studies address vaccine pricing through mathematical programming models [36, 37, 38, 39], as-
171 suming a central planner for the US market without considering supply limitations. Additional studies have
172 focused on determining how combination vaccines fit the overall schedule for the US market under a central
173 planner [40, 41, 42, 43]. While considering low- and lower-middle-income countries, Yang [24] proposes a
174 general model for vaccine distribution within a country without considering pricing.

175 Proano et al. [14] proposes an optimization-based methodology to model pricing coordination between
176 different market segments and producers in the global pediatric vaccine market, where a single coordinating
177 entity acts as a decision-maker aiming to improve affordability and profit simultaneously. Countries are
178 grouped in market segments to procure vaccines from multiple producers via a single trusted intermediary
179 who determines affordable and profitable procuring quantities and prices. The procurement is done via a
180 synchronized multi-antigen tender. The feasible prices satisfy tiered pricing constraints, ensure a desired
181 profitability to the producers, and are lower than the market's reservation prices.

182 Proano et al. [14] shows that it is possible to price vaccines affordably for all coordinated market segments
183 (including high-income markets) when the supply of combination vaccines is accessible to all market segments.
184 Additionally, Proano et al. [14] shows that the total social surplus (i.e., the total welfare resulting from
185 aggregating savings and profit) is a consequence of the choice and volume of vaccines procured.

186 Considering a hypothetically coordinated vaccine market with a single entity, Mosquera [44] extends
187 Proano et al. [14] to evaluate the effect on profits and affordability of varying the number of market segments
188 in which countries are grouped, considering uncertainty on the vaccines' reservation prices, and different levels
189 for the producers' return of investment. Mosquera [44] concludes that grouping countries into more market
190 segments improves the affordability of low-income countries while decreasing the profits of vaccine producers.

191 However, increasing the number of market segments in which low- and low-middle-income countries are
192 grouped while decreasing the number of market segments for upper-middle- and high-income countries could
193 expand affordability for low-income countries without affecting profit levels or making vaccines prohibitively
194 expensive for the high-income countries (i.e., vaccines remain priced below each market’s reservation price).
195 Mosquera [44] also shows that uncertainty in reservation prices and the return on investment rates do not
196 have a significant effect on affordability.

197 This study differentiates from Proano et al. [14] and Mosquera [44] by modeling market dynamics with
198 multiple non-cooperative coordinating entities that compete to secure higher savings for their countries while
199 maintaining a profitable market. The proposed framework allows controlling three effects absent in the
200 Proano et al. [14] and Mosquera [44] studies: the number of coordinating entities, the order of procurement
201 for those coordinating entities, and the way producers adjust their investment expectations after negotiating
202 with each entity.

203 Several studies have focused on Gavi, an existing coordinating entity for the vaccine market, and its
204 impact on countries when they are no longer eligible for its financial support[7, 45, 46]. Saxenian et al. [45]
205 evaluates the readiness of 16 countries if they stop receiving financial assistance from Gavi as they graduate,
206 concluding that the incremental financial load on graduating countries may provoke these countries to cancel
207 or scale down immunization programs and face issues with their vaccine supply [45], potentially decreasing
208 their coverage levels.

209 Frontiers [25] discusses how the GNI-based tiered pricing does not guarantee higher affordability and
210 might instead limit access to vaccines that become prohibitively expensive for countries that transition from
211 low-income to lower-middle-income. This criticism is shared by Moon et al. [26], claiming that tiered pricing
212 may overburden middle-income countries in an unsustainable manner while incentivizing producers to focus
213 on the higher profits obtained from high-income markets.

214 3 Methodology

215 This study proposes the Group Vaccine Allocation (GVA) model, a three-stage mathematical programming
216 framework, to optimize the procurement decisions of one coordinating entity at a time. We apply GVA to
217 an ordered set of coordinating entities to test the influence on affordability and profit of four factors: (F1)
218 the number of market segments in which 194 countries are grouped; (F2) the number of coordinating entities
219 facilitating procurement in the global market; (F3) the order followed by the entities in negotiating their
220 procurement plans; and (F4) the producers adjusting minimum prices to recover their return on investment
221 (i.e., offering discounts on leftover vaccine supply). Each experimental factor has multiple levels. For

222 each combination of levels in an experimental instance, we create multiple replications by randomizing the
223 vaccines' reservation prices in each market segment. For each of these experimental instances, the GVA
224 problem is sequentially solved for each coordinating entity following a procuring order. Before solving the
225 GVA for the next entity in the sequence, the overall antigen demand and vaccine supply are adjusted to
226 account for the latest entity's purchases.

227 The GVA iteratively solves a sequence of three optimization problems. For each entity in the current
228 negotiation round, the first stage determines vaccine quantities that maximize the total social surplus of
229 all market segments served by the entity. This total social surplus aggregates the markets' savings and
230 producers' profits. The second stage determines a lower bound on the prices for the procured vaccines that
231 maintain the optimal total social surplus, and the third stage determines their upper bounds. Prices per
232 dose between these bounds also maximize the total social surplus. The lower-bound prices correspond to the
233 most affordable and least profitable vaccine prices per dose, while the upper-bound prices correspond to the
234 least affordable and most profitable prices. The GVA ensures that these prices are lower than the reservation
235 prices for each vaccine at each entity's market segments. Without loss of generality, the GVA is solved for
236 a one-year procurement cycle, assuming that all countries in a global market are served by coordinating
237 entities that make procurement decisions on their behalf.

238 **3.1 GVA: Group Vaccine Allocation Model**

239 Through its three stages, the GVA determines a vaccine procurement plan and the feasible range of prices
240 per dose that maximize savings for the entity's market segments and profits for the vaccine producers (i.e.,
241 the total social surplus). The following notation and formulation describe the GVA:

242 Sets:

243 B : set of vaccines

244 A : set of antigens offered through immunization

245 E : set of coordinating entities

246 M : set of all market segments

247 M_e : set of market segments that procure through coordinating entity $e \in E$

248 P : set of vaccine producers

249 B_a^1 : set of vaccines offering antigen $a \in A$

250 Q_b : sets of vaccines that together offer the same antigen protection as vaccine $b \in B$, and are fabricated
251 by the same producer.

252 N_q : vaccines in each subset $q \in Q_b$.

253 L_t : set of all countries that qualify as $t \in \{ \text{low-income (LIC) , lower-middle-income (LMIC), upper-middle-}$
254 $\text{income (UMIC), high-income (HIC) } \}$

255 Parameters:

256 R_{bm} : Reservation price of vaccine $b \in B$ in market segment $m \in M$. The maximum price per dose that the
257 market $m \in M$ is willing to pay for vaccine $b \in B$. R_{bm} corresponds to the average reservation price
258 for countries in market m .

259 l_m : Average birth cohort per year in market $m \in M$.

260 C_b : Annualized production, research, and development fixed costs necessary to manufacture vaccine $b \in B$,
261 considering a desired rate of return.

262 d_{am} : Number of doses of antigen $a \in A$ needed to immunize a child in market $m \in M$ according to the
263 market's immunization schedule.

264 D_{bm} : Maximum number of doses of vaccine $b \in B$ allowed per child in market segment $m \in M$ to avoid over-
265 immunization (*i.e.*, children receiving more doses than recommended for any of the antigens provided
266 by vaccine $b \in B$).

267 S_b : Total supply of vaccine $b \in B$

268 \hat{s}_b : Remaining supply of vaccine $b \in B$ at the current round of negotiations, updated after each coordinating
269 entity negotiates.

270 gni_m : Average gross national income (GNI) per capita among the countries in market segment $m \in M$

271 α_{bm} : Scaling factor that increases the price per dose of vaccine $b \in B$ for market segment $m \in M$ when pur-
272 chase quantities are smaller than the available supply. It is part of an elasticity constraint incentivizing
273 larger purchases, and equal to $\frac{R_{bm}S_b}{C_b} - 1$.

274 u_b : Minimum price per dose the producer of vaccine $b \in B$ would accept.

275 ψ : Monetary penalty for every unmet dose of vaccine demand.

276 η : Monetary penalty for producing vaccines that do not add social surplus. η prevents plans in which a
 277 vaccine is produced ($g_b = 1$) but not bought ($\sum_{m \in M} X_{bm} = 0$). In the numerical example, $\eta = 1$.

278 Variables:

279 X_{bm} : Doses of vaccine $b \in B$ to be purchased by market segment $m \in M$

280 Y_{bm} : Price per dose of vaccine $b \in B$ in market segment $m \in M$

281 g_b : Binary variable indicating whether $b \in B$ is being produced (i.e., $g_b = 1$) or not (i.e., $g_b = 0$)

282 O_{am} : Unmet demand of antigen $a \in A$ in market segment $m \in M$

283 3.1.1 Stage 1: Maximizing Total Social Surplus (TSS)

For each entity $e \in E$:

$$\text{Max}_{X, Y, g} \left(\sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} R_{bm} X_{bm} - \sum_{b \in B} C_b \frac{\sum_{m \in M_e} X_{bm}}{S_b} \right) - \psi \sum_{a \in A} \sum_{m \in M_e} O_{am} - \eta \sum_{b \in B} g_b \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t. } Y_{bm} + (1 - g_b) \sum_{t \in N_q} R_{tm} \geq \sum_{t \in N_q} Y_{tm} \quad \forall b \in B, q \in Q_b : \|Q_b\| \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{m \in M_e} X_{bm} \leq \hat{s}_b g_b \quad \forall b \in B \quad (3)$$

$$Y_{bm} \geq \left[\alpha_{bm} \frac{(\hat{s}_b g_b - X_{bm})}{S_b} + g_b \right] \frac{C_b}{S_b} \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M_e : \hat{s} > 0 \quad (4)$$

$$Y_{bm} \leq R_{bm} g_b \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M_e \quad (5)$$

$$Y_{bm} \geq g_b u_b \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M_e \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{b \in B_a^i} X_{bm} + O_{am} \geq d_{am} l_m \quad \forall a \in A, m \in M_e \quad (7)$$

$$X_{bm} \leq D_{bm} l_m \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M_e \quad (8)$$

$$X_{bm} \geq 0 \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M_e \quad (9)$$

$$O_{am} \geq 0 \quad \forall a \in A, m \in M_e \quad (10)$$

$$g_b = \{0, 1\} \quad \forall b \in B \quad (11)$$

284 In Stage 1, the mixed integer programming model described above determines all procurement quantities X_{bm}
 285 of vaccine b in each of the market segments $m \in M_e$ of entity e that maximize total social surplus, penalizes
 286 not meeting antigen demands, and results in the lowest number of vaccine choices. We define the total social
 287 surplus as the sum of the total profits for producers $\left(\sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} X_{bm} Y_{bm} - \sum_{b \in B} C_b \frac{\sum_{m \in M_e} X_{bm}}{S_b} \right)$ and
 288 the total savings for the market segments $\left(\sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} (R_{bm} - Y_{bm}) X_{bm} \right)$.

289 In the non-cooperative scenario, the producers' revenue is generated from sequential negotiations between
 290 the producers and the coordinating entities. Therefore, the fraction of annualized fixed costs covered from
 291 vaccine sales can only be determined after all the entity negotiations have been completed. Additionally,
 292 GVA's Stage 1 model considers that the price per dose decreases linearly as procurement quantities increase.
 293 Failure to meet demand is possible but intensely penalized.

294 Since we aim to increase affordability for target low-income countries, the objective function in (1)
 295 simultaneously maximizes total social surplus for an entity's negotiation and, through penalty multipliers,
 296 minimizes gaps in meeting its vaccine demands. The total social surplus contribution from each entity
 297 considers the fraction of the annualized fixed costs resulting from the number of vaccines bought in the
 298 current iteration (i.e., $\frac{\sum_{m \in M} X_{bm}}{S_b}$). The closer the purchase of a vaccine is to its total supply, the higher the
 299 proportion of the fixed costs covered by the entity. The objective also minimizes the gap between the vaccine
 300 purchases and the entity's market segments' demands. The penalty term $\left(\psi \sum_{a \in A, m \in M} O_{am}\right)$ in objective
 301 (1) allows for small gaps in meeting demands. Together, this penalty term and constraint (7) ensure that the
 302 procured vaccine quantities closely meet the markets' antigen demands, avoiding infeasibility if the demand
 303 cannot be entirely satisfied. We use $\psi = 10^6$ in our numerical experiments to ensure that our solutions
 304 fulfill as much of the demand as possible (i.e., we prioritize meeting the demand for vaccines over profits or
 305 savings). The last term in (1) minimizes the number of vaccine types used in the entity's procurement plan.
 306 Note that any value of $\eta > 0$ would be sufficient to induce the desired behavior. In our numerical example,
 307 we use $\eta = 1$.

308 Constraint (2) ensures that the price negotiated for a combination vaccine is higher than the sum of
 309 the prices of the bundles of vaccines from the same producer that can offer similar antigen protection (e.g.,
 310 the price of a vaccine containing antigens for diphtheria-tetanus-pertussis (DTP) and hepatitis B is higher
 311 than buying separate vaccines against hepatitis B and DTP from the same producer). For any given vaccine
 312 $b \in B$ there is a set of vaccine bundles Q_b whose elements are sets of vaccines offering the same antigen
 313 protection as b . Each of the bundles in Q_b are vaccines made by the same producer of b . For example,
 314 consider the case of a manufacturer producing five vaccines: DTP-IPV-HiB, IPV-HiB, DTP, HiB, IPV.
 315 Then, $Q_{\text{DTP-IPV-HiB}} = \{N_1, N_2\}$ where $N_1 = \{\text{IPV-HiB, DTP}\}$, and $N_2 = \{\text{DTP, HiB, IPV}\}$. Constraint
 316 (2) ensures that the value of DTP-IPV-HiB is higher than the value of N_1 or N_2 .

317 Constraint (3) ensures that purchases do not exceed the available vaccine supply in that round of nego-
 318 tiations.

319 If coordinating entities do not cooperate, vaccine producers cannot guarantee that the annualized R&D
 320 and production fixed costs are fully recovered until all entity negotiations are completed, and all vaccine
 321 purchases are known. Thus, under a non-cooperative scenario, procurement decisions are iteratively made

322 for one coordinating entity at a time without complete information about the purchases made by other
 323 coordinating entities.

324 Constraint (4) induces economies of scale by adjusting prices per dose based on the purchased volume.
 325 If a vaccine negotiated in previous rounds still has available supply, the constraint incentivizes buying as
 326 many doses as possible in the current round. If the entire supply of a vaccine is being bought, constraint
 327 (4) guarantees the price per dose is low but sufficient to cover the annualized fixed costs (i.e., $Y_{bm} \geq \frac{C_b}{S_b}$).
 328 When purchasing less than the entire available supply, \hat{s} , prices increase by a factor α_{bm} to mitigate the risk
 329 that producers will not recover their fixed costs in following entity negotiations. The value of α_{bm} is equal
 330 to $(R_{bm} \frac{S_b}{C_b} - 1)$ and ensures that –for any produced vaccine– its price per dose remains between the lowest
 331 level necessary to cover fixed cost and its reservation prices (i.e., $\frac{C_b}{S_b} \leq Y_{bm} \leq R_{bm}$.) Appendix B describes
 332 how the value of α_{bm} is determined.

333 Constraint (5) guarantees that the negotiated prices do not exceed the reservation prices for each vaccine
 334 in each market segment. Constraint (6) forces prices per dose to be above a pre-established minimum
 335 the producer of a given vaccine $b \in B$ would be willing to accept (in our numerical example, we use
 336 $u_b = \$0.20 \forall b \in B$) [7, 47]. Constraint (7) guarantees that the coordinating entities do not buy more
 337 vaccines than their demand. Constraint (8) prevents optimal vaccine purchases for a market segment from
 338 exceeding its needs.

339 3.1.2 Stage 2: Maximizing Total Customer Surplus (TCS)

For each entity $e \in E$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max}_Y \quad \text{TCS: } & \sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} (R_{bm} - Y_{bm}) X_{bm}^* & (12) \\ \text{subject to} & \quad \text{Constraints (2), (4), (5), (6)} \end{aligned}$$

340 In Stage 2, for each entity e , a linear programming model maximizes the savings that the entity’s market
 341 segments can obtain by procuring vaccines at prices lower than their average reservation prices (i.e., the
 342 market’s reservation price), considering as inputs the vaccine quantities resulting from the solution of the
 343 Stage 1 problem (X^*). The Stage 2 problem establishes a lower bound on vaccine prices that maintain
 344 the optimal total social surplus from Stage 1 at profitable prices to the producers. At the same time, the
 345 market segments extract as much customer surplus as possible. Since profits can only be calculated once all
 346 coordinating entities complete their negotiations, the Stage 2 model determines vaccine prices that facilitate
 347 securing the desired return on investment from entity e ’s procuring decisions.

348 **3.1.3 Stage 3: Maximizing Total Profits, (TPF)**

For entity $e \in E$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max}_Y \quad & \text{TPF: } \sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} Y_{bm} X_{bm}^* - \sum_{b \in B} C_b \frac{\sum_{m \in M_e} X_{bm}^*}{S_b} \quad (13) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \text{Constraints (2), (4), (5), (6)} \end{aligned}$$

349 In Stage 3, a similar linear programming model maximizes profits for the vaccine allocations resulting
 350 from Stage 1 for entity e . This LP formulation establishes an upper bound on the vaccine prices that maintain
 351 the optimized total social surplus from Stage 1 without exceeding the reservation prices beyond R_{bm} .

352 It is assumed that all market segments can purchase any vaccine. Table 2 summarizes the constraints
 353 enforced at each stage of the GVA for an entity and a problem instance.

354 While in a fully cooperative market, it is possible to estimate the global profit. In a non-cooperative
 355 framework with a sequential procurement process, it is not trivial to determine how much of the fixed costs
 356 are covered by negotiating with each coordinating entity. For this reason, the objective function (13) is
 357 similar to (4) but considers that the annualized fixed costs are proportional to the fraction of the supply sold
 358 to the entity. Since the total profits cannot be estimated until all entities have completed their procurement,
 359 we also report on the actual revenue. Finally, after each entity negotiation round, any remaining supply is
 360 available for subsequent coordinating entities.

361 The feasible region ((2)-(11)) for the Stage 1 problem of a coordinated fully cooperative framework is less
 362 restrictive than the feasible region of a non-cooperative framework because the latter is solved iteratively for
 363 each coordinating entity. Hence, the total social surplus of a cooperative framework is an upper bound for
 364 the total social surplus of a non-cooperative framework.

365 The results of Stages 2 and 3 depend on the procurement plans determined in Stage 1. Hence, their
 366 feasible regions are not necessarily the same for the cooperative and non-cooperative frameworks (e.g., vaccine
 367 purchases for the fully cooperative framework may not be the same as determined by coordinating entities
 368 optimizing savings for their own subset of market segments). Therefore, the non-cooperative negotiation can
 369 extract a greater total customer surplus or total profit than a fully cooperative market. Nevertheless, the
 370 total social surplus of a non-cooperative negotiation remains lower than that of a fully cooperative framework.

371 After the GVA has been applied to all entities, the overall profit corresponds to the revenue obtained
 372 from sales to all entities minus the annualized fixed costs for all procured vaccines. Producing a vaccine is
 373 not financially sustainable if it has negative profit even at the highest acceptable price levels in the optimal
 374 procurement plan. Similarly, a vaccine is guaranteed to do financially well if the profit is positive, even at

375 the lowest prices.

Stage	Variables	Objective Function	Constraints
1	X_{bm}, Y_{bm}, g_b	(1)	(2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7), (8), (9), (11)
2	Y_{bm}	(12)	(2), (4), (5), (6)
3	Y_{bm}	(13)	(2), (4), (5), (6)

Table 2: Decision variables and constraints used in each stage problem.

376 3.2 Experimental framework

377 We design experimental scenarios by controlling four key factors: (F1) the number of market segments in
 378 which 194 countries are grouped; (F2) the number of coordinating entities facilitating procurement in the
 379 global market; (F3) the order followed by the entities in negotiating their procurement plans; and (F4) the
 380 producers' decision of adjusting or not their minimum prices to recover their return on investment. Table 3
 381 summarizes the experimental scenarios tested to answer the research questions.

382 For factor (F1), 194 countries are grouped into 2, 4, 8, or 12 different market segments based on the
 383 similarity of their average GNI per capita, gni_m . The market segments are then ranked based on their average
 384 income per capita and assigned to coordinating entities so that the entities make procurement decisions for
 385 an equal number of market segments. For example, in a scenario with 2 coordinating entities and 12 market
 386 segments, the first coordinating entity would be responsible for the 6 market segments with the highest gni_m ,
 387 and the second coordinating entity would be assigned the 6 market segments with the lowest gni_m .

388 Factor (F2) allows the number of non-cooperative coordinating entities to vary in six levels (1, 2, 3, 4, 6,
 389 12). Under an equal distribution of market segments per entity, if the number of market segments is 12, the
 390 number of markets per entity decreases (12, 6, 4, 3, 2, and 1) as the number of entities increases (1, 2, 3, 4,
 391 6, and 12). The maximum number of entities used per experimental scenario equals the number of market
 392 segments. The case when a single coordinating entity serves all market segments is considered a benchmark
 393 scenario. Hence, there is a benchmark scenario for each number of markets segments in which countries are
 394 clustered.

395 For factor (F3), the coordinating entities' procurement order can be ascending or descending based on

Factors	Levels					
F1: Number of market segments	2	4	8	12		
F2: Number of coordinating entities	1	2	3	4	6	12
F3: Coordinating entities procurement order	Ascending income			Descending income		
F4: Fixed cost recovering policies	Adjusted			Invariant		

Table 3: Experimental factors and levels

396 the average wealth of their market segments (i.e., gni_m). In practice, high-income markets are the first to
 397 purchase and secure vaccine access, which is captured by a descending procuring order. The descending
 398 procuring order may be favored by producers, given their need to secure profit rapidly. In contrast, the
 399 ascending order incentivizes large volume purchases to be secured first.

400 For factor (F4), producers follow either an ‘adjusted’ or ‘invariant’ pricing policy. As stated earlier,
 401 producers estimate a minimum price per vaccine dose considering the annualized fixed R&D production costs
 402 to be recovered. With an ‘adjusted’ policy, if part of a vaccine’s supply has been sold to some coordinating
 403 entities, producers adjust their vaccine prices for subsequent negotiations to try meeting their annualized
 404 fixed costs goals. This is achieved by updating these goals after each entity negotiation, as shown in Algorithm
 405 1, consequently changing the bounds of Constraint (4). In the ‘invariant’ policy, at the beginning of the
 406 procuring cycle, producers estimate the minimum price needed to recover the entire annualized fixed costs
 407 and keep it fixed during the procurement sequence. In practice, adjusting the bounds of Constraint (4)
 408 allows coordinating entities to pay a lower price per dose for a vaccine that has already been purchased by
 409 another entity and still has leftover supply. This strategy is equivalent to a "discount price" to incentivize
 410 buyers to purchase leftover supply instead of setting up production for a new vaccine.

411 The four-factor level combinations result in 60 experimental scenarios. For each scenario, we randomize
 412 each vaccine’s reservation prices (at each market) from 90% to 110% of their baseline reservation prices.
 413 Vaccines with no available historical data had their reservation prices estimated as a function of each market
 414 segment’s income and historical prices for other vaccines offering similar antigens, as described in Mosquera
 415 [44]. We generate 1,000 random instances for each experimental scenario. For each random instance, we iter-
 416 atively solve the GVA three-stage optimization process for each procuring entity as illustrated in Algorithm
 417 1.

Algorithm 1 Solution Procedure

- 1: **for** each coordinating entity $e \in E$ **do**
 - 2: Solve the GVA
 - 3: Determine which vaccines to produce
 - 4: Determine vaccine quantities to buy for each market segment $m \in M_e$
 - 5: Define upper and lower price bounds per vaccine dose
 - 6: **for every** vaccine $b \in B$ **do**
 - 7: **if** Adjusted policy is used **then**
 - 8: Update remaining fixed cost: $C_b \leftarrow C_b$ minus revenue obtained from selling $b \in B$ to $m \in M_e$
 - 9: Update available supply: $\hat{s}_b \leftarrow \hat{s}_b$ minus volume of b purchased by $m \in M_e$
 - 10: Collect output metrics.
-

418 3.3 Output Metrics

419 For all experimental scenarios, we monitor the following metrics:

- 420 • the aggregated profits for the producers,
- 421 • the aggregated savings for all market segments, and
- 422 • savings and revenue generated by LIC, LMIC, UMIC, and HIC (based on the World Bank classification)
423 as they are grouped in different market segments.

424 A market’s savings in procuring a vaccine (i.e., customer surplus) is reported by the difference between the
425 market’s reservation price and the mid-price between the lower and upper price bounds determined in Stages
426 2 and 3 of the GVA process. The mid-price may be interpreted as the price negotiated when both savings
427 and profits have equal bargaining power. Using the mid-prices allows our analysis to focus on the research
428 questions proposed for this study. Given that the price countries are willing to pay is randomized for each
429 experimental scenario, the dollar value of the global vaccine market is also random. Hence, we normalize our
430 metrics over the market dollar value of each experimental instance. Table 4 summarizes the set of metrics
431 used in this study. Appendix A offers additional details on the experimental results, including the number of
432 producers who do not cover annualized fixed costs for their vaccines, the number of times market segments
433 do not satisfy all of their antigen demands, savings, and revenue per country.

434

435 4 Experimental data

436 This study considers a vaccine market consisting of 14 producers offering 52 vaccines to satisfy demands
437 for 6 different antigens (1. Hib: Haemophilus Influenza type B, 2. HepB: Hepatitis B, 3. DTP: Diphtheria
438 Tetanus and Pertussis, 4. V: Varicella, 5. MMR: Measles, Mumps and Rubella, and 6. IPV: Polio) (see
439 Table 5); 194 countries are grouped by their GNI per capita into market segments for tier-pricing purposes.
440 Rather than having only the usual 4-tier market segmentation (i.e., high-income, upper-middle-income, lower-
441 middle-income, and low-income countries based on the World Bank classification [9]), we rank countries in
442 descending order by their GNI per capita and group them in either 2, 4, 8, or 12 market segments (see Table
443 6). Consequently, each vaccine has a different average reservation price in each market segment. In this
444 study, all variations of diphtheria-tetanus-pertussis vaccines and all polio vaccines are assumed to offer the
445 same type of antigens and are represented by DTP and IPV, respectively.

Metric	Description	Mathematical Expression
Total Customer Surplus (TCS)	Savings received from the vaccine procurement of all market segments of all coordinating entities	$\sum_{e \in E} \sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} (R_{bm} - Y_{bm}) X_{bm}$
Market Value (MV)	The total monetary value in the vaccine market. Sum of all customer savings and all profit.	$TCS + \sum_{e \in E} \sum_{m \in M_e} \sum_{b \in B} (X_{bm} Y_{bm} - C_b g_b)$
$\frac{TCS}{MV}$	Total customer surplus across all entities as a fraction of the market values.	$\frac{TCS}{MV}$
$\frac{CS_t}{MV}$	Customer surplus in market segment $t \in$ (low-income, lower-middle-income, upper-middle-income, high-income) as a fraction of the market value.	$\frac{\sum_{e \in E} \sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in L_t} (R_{bm} - Y_{bm}) X_{bm}}{MV}$
$\frac{TPF}{MV}$	Total profit across all entities as a fraction of the market value.	$\sum_{e \in E} \left(\frac{\sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} (X_{bm} \cdot Y_{bm} - C_b g_b)}{MV} \right)$
$\frac{TSS}{MV}$	Total social surplus across all entities as a fraction of the market value.	$\sum_{e \in E} \left(\frac{\sum_{b \in B} \sum_{m \in M_e} (X_{bm} \cdot R_{bm} - C_b g_b)}{MV} \right)$

Table 4: Variables used as performance metrics and their explanations.

Producer ID	Vaccine ID	Antigens in the Vaccine
1	6	HepB
	41	DTP, HepB and Hib
2	20	IPV
	1	DTP
3	7	HepB
	32	DTP and HepB
	42	DTP, HepB and Hib
4	2	DTP
	43	DTP, HepB and Hib
5	8	HepB
	14	Hib
6	3	DTP
	9	HepB
	15	Hib
	21	IPV
	25	MMR
	29	V
	33	DTP and HepB
	38	DTP and IPV
	44	DTP, HepB and Hib
49	DTP, HepB and IPV	
51	DTP, HepB, Hib and IPV	
7	10	HepB

Producer ID	Vaccine ID	Antigens in the Vaccine
	45	DTP, HepB and Hib
8	11	HepB
	16	Hib
	26	MMR
	30	V
	39	HepB and Hib
	40	MMR and V
9	17	Hib
	35	DTP and Hib
10	46	DTP, HepB and Hib
11	4	DTP
	18	Hib
	22	IPV
	27	MMR
	31	V
	36	DTP and Hib
	50	DTP, Hib and IPV
52	DTP, HepB, Hib and IPV	
12	5	DTP
	12	HepB
	19	Hib
	23	IPV
	28	MMR
	34	DTP and HepB
	37	DTP and Hib
47	DTP, HepB and Hib	
13	13	HepB
14	24	IPV

Table 5: Vaccines in each producer portfolio. Vaccines and producers are referred by their study IDs. Antigens in each vaccine correspond to: (Hib= Haemophilus influenzae type B, DTP= Diphtheria-Tetanus-Pertussis, HepB=Hepatitis B, V=varicella, MMR=Measles-Mumps-Rubella, IPV= inactivated polio). Data was aggregated from WHO’s V3P repository, 2018 [48].

446 5 Results

447 5.1 Experimental benchmarks

448 For each of the 60 experimental scenarios, we compare key metrics to a benchmark where all market segments
449 receive procurement recommendations from a single coordinating entity. As a result, there is a different
450 benchmark for each number of market segments in which the global vaccine market is divided (i.e., 2, 4,
451 8, or 12). Each benchmark mimics a fully coordinated system for a given number of market segments in

Number of market segments	Market segment IDs	Country IDs assigned to the market segment
12	1	1 to 5
	2	6 to 26
	3	27 to 57
	4	58 to 65
	5	66 to 75
	6	76 to 109
	7	110 to 113
	8	114 to 134
	9	135 to 158
	10	159 to 172
	11	173 to 191
	12	192 to 194
8	1	1 and 2
	2	3 to 57
	3	58 to 65
	4	66 to 109
	5	110 to 123
	6	124 to 158
	7	159 to 180
	8	181 to 194
4	1	1 to 57
	2	58 to 109
	3	110 to 158
	4	159 to 194
2	1	1 to 131
	2	132 to 194
1	1	1 to 194

Table 6: Country-to-market segment assignment based on the number of market segments in the experimental scenarios. Country 1 correspond to the country with highest gni_m based on the World Bank classification, while country 194 corresponds to the one with lowest gni_m

452 which there is no need to follow any procurement order nor adjust the recovery of the annualized fixed costs,
453 and all tenders are synchronized. Note that the only factor with multiple levels for this benchmark is the
454 number of market segments, explored already in Mosquera [44] that shows that a higher number of market
455 segments increases Total Social Surplus. Figure 1 shows changes in Total Social Surplus for different levels
456 of the three factors introduced in this study.

457 For clarity and brevity, and without loss of generality, this section contrasts the results collected for
458 experimental scenarios with countries grouped in 12 market segments, given that Figure 1 shows that a
459 higher number of market segments leads to higher Total Social Surplus). Results for scenarios with 2, 4, and
460 8 market segments are available in Appendix A and ratify the trends described in this section. The output
461 metrics are computed considering the mid-point prices between the lowest and highest feasible prices per
462 vaccine dose for each market segment.

Figure 1: Aggregated $\frac{TSS}{MV}$ for a global vaccine market when the number of market segments changes. Results compare ascending and descending negotiation policies, considering invariant or adjusted discounts, when the number of coordinating entities (CE) is 2 or 4. Total social surplus increases when there are more market segments in the negotiation process.

5.2 Global-level effects: Aggregated results across market segments

Figure 2 illustrates the Total Social Surplus as a fraction of the dollar value of the global market ($\frac{TSS}{MV}$) for each experimental instance. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the Total Customer Surplus ($\frac{TCS}{MV}$) and Total Profit ($\frac{TPF}{MV}$) considering the mid-point prices of the feasible price range resulting from the three-stage optimization process. Figures 5 to 12 illustrate the customer surplus and revenue for specific market segments grouped into the World Bank classification as low-, lower-middle-, upper-middle- and high-income countries.

Figure 2 shows that total social surplus ($\frac{TSS}{MV}$) increases as the number of coordinating entities decreases, or – since the number of market segments is equally distributed by the number of entities in each experiment – as the number of market segments handled by each entity increases. These results illustrate that the $\frac{TSS}{MV}$, and hence the global market’s aggregated affordability and profit expand when the market is more cooperative (i.e., fewer coordinating entities) and when entities leverage on tiered pricing opportunities by coordinating a large number of market segments. As discussed in section 3, this is an expected result given the less restrictive nature of a fully cooperative coordinated negotiation. Scenarios with an invariant pricing policy had higher TSS than those with an adjusted policy.

Figure 3 shows that the overall profitability ($\frac{TPF}{MV}$) increases as the number of coordinating entities decreases (or equivalently, as the number of markets per entity increases) in a similar trend to the $\frac{TSS}{MV}$. Furthermore, scenarios following a ‘descending’ procuring policy perform better than those following an

Figure 2: Aggregated $\frac{TSS}{MV}$ for a global vaccine market with 12 market segments, for a varying number of coordinating entities, different procurement priority orders, and different fixed cost recovery policies. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. For all scenarios, $\frac{TSS}{MV}$ increases as the number of entities decreases. Other factors have a smaller impact, but descending order with invariant pricing policy dominates.

Figure 3: Aggregated $\frac{TPF}{MV}$ in the global vaccine market with 12 market segments, for a varying number of coordinating entities, different procurement priorities, and choice of fixed cost recovery policy. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. $\frac{TPF}{MV}$ decreases as the number of entities increase in a similar shape as the $\frac{TSS}{MV}$.

480 'ascending' policy in all cases with less than 6 coordinating entities. This Figure also shows that the vaccine
 481 producers are not able to leverage discounts with the 'adjusted' pricing policy to increase overall profits. On

482 the contrary, the discounted prices result in lower profits in all scenarios. The remaining Figures follow the
 483 same trend of lower profits or revenue when using the 'adjusted' pricing policy.

Figure 4: Aggregated $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ in a global vaccine market with 12 market segments, varying number of coordinating entities, different procurement priorities, and choice of fixed cost recovery policy. The horizontal line represents the value for the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. Unlike Figures 2 and 3, $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ increases as the number of entities increase, and performs better under an adjusted pricing policy.

484 Figure 4 shows that the overall market affordability (i.e., aggregated total customer surplus across all
 485 entities) increases when there are more entities or, equivalently, when the number of market segments per
 486 entity decreases. Additionally, there is little difference in total customer surplus resulting from adopting an
 487 'ascending' or 'descending' procuring order (around 1% for the scenario with 2 coordinating entities.) The
 488 magnitude of the Total Customer Surplus is lower than the Total Profits in Figure 3 (maximum $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ of
 489 around 18% compared to the maximum $\frac{TPF}{MV}$ of around 60%. Therefore, the Total Social Surplus in Figure
 490 2 (i.e., the sum of both metrics) follows the profit trends and decreases when there are more entities.

491 5.3 Market-level effects at the LIC, LMIC, UMIC, and HIC

492 Figures 5 and 6 show that producers can extract more revenue from sales to LIC and LMIC under an
 493 ascending policy and a higher number of coordinating entities. The revenue levels are not significantly
 494 affected by any other factor when the procurement order is descending. The relatively constant revenue seen
 495 in the descending negotiation order suggests that the available vaccines are bought at near reservation price
 496 levels, regardless of the number of coordinating entities.

497 The revenue for UMIC and HIC (Figures 7 and 8) follows the total profit trends (Figure 3), where revenue

Figure 5: Revenue obtained from sales to low-income countries (LIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. Revenue tends to increase as the number of coordinating entities increases, and an ascending procuring order is used. Under a descending procuring order, the revenue is insensitive to the number of coordinating entities.

Figure 6: Revenue from lower-middle-income countries (LMIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. Ascending order dominates the descending procuring order.

498 increases as the number of entities decreases. Sales to markets with higher reservation prices contribute the
 499 most to profit gains, even if their sales volumes are lower than other markets (Figures 5 and 6). The revenue
 500 from all income groups decreases when vaccine producers offer discounts on leftover products through the

Figure 7: Revenue from sales to upper-middle-income countries (UMIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. A descending priority procuring order offers higher revenue from sales to UMIC than an ascending order.

Figure 8: Revenue from sales to high-income countries (HIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. Revenue increases with fewer coordinating entities. The descending order dominates the ascending order, while the fixed cost recovering policy seems to have little to no effect.

501 'adjusted' pricing policy, which explains the decrease in profits seen in Figure 3. Therefore, regardless of the
 502 increase in savings experienced by LIC in Figure 9, vaccine producers are unlikely to adopt an 'adjusted'
 503 pricing policy.

Figure 9: $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ for low-income countries (LIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ for LIC is very sensitive to procuring order. Descending priority provides overall higher TCS, especially with a higher number of coordinating entities.

504 LIC can ensure a modest customer surplus, between 1 and 5% of the MV. Figure 9 shows that customer
 505 surplus for LIC decreases with a fewer number of entities under a ‘descending’ procuring order. The same
 506 decreasing TCS pattern can be observed for LMIC regardless of procurement order (Figure 10). However,
 507 for LIC and LMIC, the descending procuring policy offers more TCS. Figures 11 and 12 show that for UMIC
 508 and HIC customer surplus increases as the number of entities decreases, in particular under the ascending
 509 procuring policy.

510 5.4 Country-level effects

511 A low Total Customer Surplus at the market level is not necessarily bad news. The GVA framework ensures
 512 that vaccine prices per dose are lower than the average reservation prices of the countries in each market.
 513 Consequently, in any market segment, it is possible that even when the market secures a positive customer
 514 surplus, its recommended vaccine prices are unaffordable to some of its countries. Low customer surplus at
 515 a market level can also result when a market’s recommended prices are closer to its countries’ reservation
 516 prices. This is especially true when the countries in the market segment have similar reservation prices; or
 517 when countries are grouped in an increasing number of market segments.

518 Figures 13 and 14 show the affordability gaps (i.e., the difference between a country’s reservation price and
 519 its market recommended price) for LICs, for ascending and descending procurement orders under adjusted

Figure 10: $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ for lower-middle-income countries (LMIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ for LMIC improves with a higher number of coordinating entities. The descending procuring order dominates the ascending procuring order. The choice of fixed cost recovering policy has an insignificant effect on the response.

Figure 11: $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ for upper-middle-income countries (UMIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line corresponds to the value for the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. The ascending negotiating order dominates the descending order. Scenarios with an 'adjusted' pricing policy dominate invariant policy for the same number of entities.

520 prices (Figure 9 illustrates the market customer surplus for these scenarios.) Figures 13 and 14 show that
 521 although the TCS/MV decreases for a single coordinating entity, the affordability gaps are less dispersed

Figure 12: $\frac{TCS}{MV}$ for high-income countries (HIC) across all experimental scenarios for 12 market segments. The horizontal line represents the value for the baseline scenario with a single coordinating entity. Affordability decreases as the number of coordinating entities increases. Ascending priority dominates results, while there is little impact when using an adjusted pricing policy

522 and less negative when segmentation per entity increases (i.e., cooperation increases). In these figures, the
 523 interquartile ranges in the boxplots are narrower, although the whisker lengths and outliers increase. Thus,
 524 increasing cooperation makes countries pay closer to their reservation prices and reduces the number of
 525 countries paying more than their reservation prices.

526 A practical implication of these results is that given enough supply, organizations procuring on behalf of
 527 lower-income countries can redirect customer surplus to target countries by procuring after higher-income
 528 market segments. Additionally, these organizations should group their participating countries in as many
 529 market segments as possible and start procurement negotiations sequentially, in descending order, starting
 530 with market segments that have higher gmi_m . This implies that as long as producers offer discounts for high-
 531 volume purchases and demand is elastic in price, organizations such as UNICEF can benefit from scheduling
 532 their tenders after markets with higher income levels, and organize the participating countries internally into
 533 multiple market segments rather than considering them part of a single-price market for LICs and LMICs.

534 6 Conclusions

535 Our results suggest that under a non-cooperative vaccine market, there are opportunities to concentrate
 536 savings on LIC and LMIC and generate profit from sales to UMIC and HIC while maintaining affordable
 537 prices for all countries, regardless of their income level. This study suggests that affordability at the market

Affordability Gap per Country
Adjusted Pricing, 12 CE vs. 1 CE, Ascending Order
Three LIC Market Segments

Figure 13: Savings per dose across all vaccines for low-income countries for a 12 market scenario with with 1 and 12 coordinating entities, following an ascending procuring order and an adjusted fixed cost recovering policy. Different colors represent different market segments.

Affordability Gap per Country
Adjusted Pricing, 12 CE vs. 1 CE, Descending Order
Three LIC Market Segments

Figure 14: Savings per dose across all vaccines for low-income countries for a 12 market scenario, with 1 and 12 coordinating entities, following a descending procuring order and an adjusted fixed cost recovering policy. Different colors represent different market segments.

538 level for low-income and low-middle-income countries can be improved by having more coordinating entities
 539 for LIC countries or effectively having a coordinating entity for LIC countries organized in a high number of
 540 market segments that procure sequentially. However, producers would see lower profit levels when negotiating
 541 with multiple coordinating entities, primarily due to a revenue decrease from high- and upper-middle-income

542 countries despite gains from sales to LIC.

543 Additionally, comparing the fixed costs recovering policies, adjusting the annualized fixed-cost expenses
544 based on the volume of vaccines that remain to sell is less effective than an ‘invariant’ policy. Furthermore,
545 ordering the entities by descending GNI helps prevent losses for producers by extracting higher revenue from
546 higher-income countries.

547 The trend in Figure 9 suggests that to increase customer surplus while guaranteeing a desired profit level
548 for the producers, the vaccine market should organize low- and lower-middle-income countries into more non-
549 cooperating entities, and high- and upper-middle-income countries in fewer coordinating entities. In practical
550 terms, this also implies that entities with LIC and LMIC countries group them in a higher number of market
551 segments procuring sequentially in descending GNI per capita. Currently, in the global vaccine market,
552 low-income countries pool-procure through a few coordinating entities (e.g., UNICEF and PAHO) under a
553 single-market segment. In contrast, higher-income countries negotiate independently and have different price
554 levels. Gavi’s and PAHO’s efforts to innovate market dynamics have incentivized pooled procurement for
555 LIC and LMIC through large single-price markets, which are equivalent to procuring through a few large,
556 coordinating entities with a single-price policy per vaccine dose. Our study suggests that if the market is
557 not entirely cooperative, having a higher number of price levels per coordinating entity offers more saving
558 opportunities, especially when low-income countries buy vaccines after higher-income countries (UMIC and
559 HIC). Ordering the negotiation by decreasing GNI may lead to lower coverage if there is a limited supply
560 of vaccines. Under such conditions, following an ascending negotiating order can still generate customer
561 surplus for low-income countries while securing additional access to vaccines. Maintaining a high level of
562 market segmentation could induce most countries to pay close to – but still below – their reservation price.

563 This study shares insights from an academic experiment that assumes that all procuring entities aim
564 to buy vaccines affordably and ensure that producers obtain the desired return on their sales. Under this
565 hypothetically altruistic buying, there are opportunities to enhance affordability by controlling when coun-
566 tries buy vaccines and how the pool procurement structure is organized. The current procurement already
567 has incentives to follow the optimal procuring order, but reductions in supply availability might make it
568 beneficial to have incentives for procuring following an ascending order.

569 Our modeling effort aims to understand if there are better ways of procuring and deploying vaccines than
570 the status quo in a non-cooperative market with price discounts by volume. We rely on an optimization-
571 based approach to generate insights for synchronizing a global vaccine market. We do not expect all existing
572 coordinating entities to embrace a mathematically-based procurement. However, we believe that our rec-
573 ommendations can provoke a reconsideration of whether entities such as Gavi and PAHO should continue
574 having single-price levels. This study suggests extending pooled procurement to UMICs and HICs can offer

575 a revenue cushion to mitigate global profit losses when the global pediatric vaccine market is synchronized
 576 to offer more affordability to LICs.

577 Appendix

578 Appendix A: Additional figures and results

579 All figures generated for this study and additional results for different market-entity configurations are
 580 available at the GitHub repository at

581 https://github.com/ba8641/ME_General.git.

582 Appendix B: Price elasticity: determining α_{bm}

583 Section 3.1.1 described that constraint (4) aims to incentivize entities to purchase as much as possible of
 584 the vaccine supply that remains to be sold after previous entities have completed their negotiations. The
 585 incentive increases the vaccine price if the buyers do not buy all the available supply, helping recover fixed
 586 costs and allowing prices to be as low as possible if the order is equivalent to the available supply.

587 Consider constraint (4): $Y_{bm} \geq \left[\frac{(\hat{s}_b - X_{bm})\alpha_{bm}}{S_b} + g_b \right] \frac{C_b}{S_b} \quad \forall b \in B, m \in M_e : \hat{s}_b > 0$

588 Determining a value for α_{bm}

589 The minimum price per dose to recover the fixed cost investment C_b with a supply S_b is such that $Y_{bm} \geq \frac{C_b}{S_b}$.
 590 If not all the supply of a vaccine b has been bought by previous entity negotiations, constraint (4) increases
 591 the price per dose by a factor $\left(\left(\frac{\hat{s}_b}{S_b} \alpha_{bm} \right) + 1 \right)$, unless all the remaining supply is allocated (i.e., $X_{bm} = \hat{s}_b$).
 592 Allocating the remaining supply ensures that the price per dose could still be the minimum needed.

However, due to constraint (5), the incremental price per dose cannot be higher than the reservation price R_{bm} . Consider the case where the unsold vaccine supply is close to the original maximum supply $\hat{s}_b \approx S_b$. To prevent a small order quantity, $X_{bm} \approx 0$, it is necessary to increase the price per dose so that its gap with its lower bound is as high as possible, making it attractive to buy larger volumes. In this case, the highest penalty brings the price to its reservation price. Hence,

$$R_{bm} = Y_{bm} = \left[\frac{(\hat{s}_b - 0)\alpha_{bm}}{S_b} + 1 \right] \frac{C_b}{S_b}$$

593 Solving for α_{bm} then result on $\alpha_{bm} = R_{bm} \frac{S_b}{C_b} - 1$, which is used as a parameter to constraint (4).

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